

rice mitochondria and their nature can be shown with the help of the lectins.

We used the concanavalin A (Con A) gold conjugates. This lectin has sugar specificity: D-mannose > D-glucose > N-acetyl D-glucosamine. Rice mitochondria were isolated, fixed, incubated in 20% Con A gold conjugate solution in

phosphate buffered saline (PBS), and studied under an electron microscope.

The rice mitochondrion surface membrane binds the Con A gold conjugate (i.e., contains Con A receptors, probably D-mannose) (Fig. 1, 2). When stained with Os, the rice mitochondrion surface looks as if it consists of global

grains. This is probably the result of protein structure distribution.

The golden deposits structure looks like a ramified tree. Evidently this is connected with the fact that the lectin carbohydrate receptors are parts of the polymer chains. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in calcareous soils

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We compared the performance of stem- and root-nodulating *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure (GM) crop, and *S. aculeata*, the GM crop commonly grown in Bihar, with different levels of inorganic fertilizer in an irrigated ricefield during 1987-89 wet season (May-Dec).

Soils were silt-loam with pH 8.5, 0.60% organic C, and 272-16-119 kg available NPK/ha.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were broadcast the third week of May at 30 kg seed/ha. When needed, 17.6 kg P/ha was basal applied. To ensure germination, one irrigation was applied 5 d before sowing.

The GM crops were incorporated 45 d after sowing; on the same day, 35- to 40-d-old seedlings of 150-d-duration

rice variety Radha were transplanted. K was basal applied at 16.6 kg/ha in all plots. P and N were applied per treatment (see table).

GM plant stands were uniform in all plots. Dry matter production and N yield were estimated at incorporation.

S. rostrata added more dry matter and N than *S. aculeata* in all treatments. P

applied at sowing of GM crops was superior to P applied at puddling.

Highest grain yields (3.1-3.3 ma) were with recommended fertilizers; with *S. rostrata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits; and with *S. aculeata* plus P and 40 kg N/ha in two equal splits. Straw yields with these treatments followed the same trend. Net returns were higher with *S. rostrata* plus P and N. ■

Effect of GM crops on rice yield and net return per rupee of investment on pooled (1987, 1988, and 1989) basis, Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	Dry matter from GM (t/ha)	N accumulated (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		Net return
			Grain	Straw	
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.2	76.2	3.1	5.1	1.10
<i>S. aculeata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	72.4	2.8	4.7	1.08
<i>S. rostrata</i> + P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.3	81.5	3.3	5.5	1.24
<i>S. rostrata</i> + no P + 40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	4.0	75.0	2.9	4.8	1.15
40 kg N/ha in 2 equal splits: MT + PI	-	-	2.4	3.9	0.71
80-40-20 kg NPK/ha	-	-	3.3	5.4	1.20
<i>S. aculeata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.0	12.3	2.4	4.0	0.85
<i>S. rostrata</i> + recommended 40-20 kg PK/ha	4.1	16.4	2.5	4.2	0.93
Control (no GM, no NPK)	-	-	1.8	2.8	0.51
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.3	0.4	0.12

^aMT = maximum tillering, PI = panicle initiation, GM = green manure.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Kresek in mature rice plants

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We found kresek in mature rice plants during 1990 in rainfed lowland fields at the BRRI Regional Station experimental farm and in farmers' fields in Barisal. This is the first report of this disease in Bangladesh.

Infested tiller showing normal older leaves and leaf sheaths.

The first symptom appears in the youngest leaf as dense whitish stripes or lesions at the base of the leaf blade. This whitish lesion moves upward through the midrib, which turns brown. Gradually, the leaf turns yellow and rolls along the midrib. It looks like deadheart caused by stem borer, but the dead leaf cannot be pulled up easily. Older leaves and leaf sheaths remain normal and green (see figure).

When a diseased tiller is split, the entire leaf base enclosed by the older leaf sheath appears soft and rotten and